

Mendelian randomization study on vitamin C and COVID-19 may be misleading

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Comment on:

Chen S, Zheng C, Chen T, Huang D, Pan Y, Chen S.

Relationship Between Plasma Vitamin C and COVID-19 Susceptibility and Severity: A Two-Sample Mendelian Randomization Study.

Front Med (Lausanne). 2022 Mar 9;9:844228.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35355592>

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Chen et al. concluded from their Mendelian randomization study that “no correlation was observed between plasma Vitamin C levels and COVID-19 susceptibility and severity” [1].

The Chen et al. study was based on an earlier study, which identified 11 plasma vitamin C-associated SNPs explaining 1.87% of the variance of plasma vitamin C [2]. However, Chen et al. did not consider which kinds of plasma vitamin C levels their Mendelian randomization study would correspond to.

From the 1.87% explanation of variance, and the data about the plasma vitamin C means and SD levels available in the earlier paper [2], we calculated that the Mendelian randomization study by Chen et al. would correspond to the comparison of two population groups of equal size with vitamin C levels of 47.3 vs. 52.7 μM [3]. Such a comparison is not clinically relevant.

With low dietary vitamin C intakes, plasma levels can fall below 10 μM , whereas with high dietary intakes, plasma levels can increase to over 80 μM (see Fig. 1C on [4]). It is important to take into account this eightfold range of plasma vitamin C levels when considering the dose-health relationship in the community, but that was not done by Chen et al. [1].

Low plasma vitamin C levels are not uncommon. Levels below 11 μM were reported, for example, in 25% of men and 16% of women from low-income populations in the UK [5], and in

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

13% of a US cohort [6]. In many population groups in the less developed countries, such low vitamin C levels are even more common [7]. Thus, large segments of the population have vitamin C levels that are less than one fifth of the “low” plasma vitamin C level corresponding to the Chen et al. analysis.

Based on the large variation in the plasma levels of vitamin C in the population, the most relevant comparison is between low and high plasma levels, e.g., 10–20 μM vs. 60–100 μM . If a study compares small variations within the high intake range only, the comparison is uninformative about possible effects of vitamin C in the low intake range.

Vitamin C may, or may not, influence COVID-19 [8,9]. However, the study by Chen et al. does not inform us about whether the risk might be increased with plasma levels of 10-20 μM .

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